

Hydrolysis of Aliphatic Esters in Presence of Mixed-oxide Catalysts

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Hydrolysis of methylacetate and ethylacetate catalysed by $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{SiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$, $\text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$, $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ mixed-oxides have been studied and found to be reactions of the first order with respect to ester concentrations. The rate constant K for the hydrolysis of methyl acetate is greater than that for ethylacetate. The values of K decrease as the acidity of the catalyst decreases. The energy of activation for the hydrolysis of methylacetate is lower than that for the hydrolysis of ethylacetate.

The value of K was also obtained from the hydrolysis of these esters in the presence of HCl (0.46 moles). The acidities of the catalysts were calculated from the ratios of the rate constants and the molar strength of HCl for each of the catalyst in the case of both the esters. The agreement between the calculated and the observed values of the acidities at $\text{pK}_a \leq -3.0$ shows that the acid centres of $\text{pK}_a \leq -3.0$ alone are able to catalyse the hydrolysis of these esters.

THE work on ester hydrolysis in the presence of catalysts in heterogeneous systems reported so far pertains mainly to the work using ion exchange resins as catalysts^{1,2}. It has been observed previously by Figoli *et al.*³ and Matsuzaki⁴ that catalysts treated with water still exhibit acidity, hence it, was considered of interest to study the hydrolysis of esters catalysed by some mixed oxides for which no data exist.

The surface acidities of these mixed oxides have already been reported by the authors of this work⁵. The work of ester hydrolysis has been extended further to the study of comparison of the kinetics of a reaction catalysed by solid acid and by an acid in solution to provide useful information about active acid centres present on the surface.

Experimental

AnalaR quality methylacetate and ethylacetate were further purified and used in the present work. All other reagents were pure grade chemicals.

Preparation of catalysts: The binary metal oxides were prepared from AnalaR quality chemicals by the precipitation and coprecipitation technique⁶. The mixtures of the precipitated hydroxides or the impregnated oxides were digested for several hours and then filtered, washed thoroughly and dried. The samples were powdered and only such of samples as were collected between 100 and 150 mesh sieves were used. The powders thus obtained were subjected to heat treatment to the desired temperature for 6 hr in an electric furnace with temperature control arrangement. The samples after heat treatment were cooled in a desiccator and preserved in covered glass tubes, under vacuum.

Measurement of surface acidity and acid strength: The acid amounts and acid strengths of catalysts were measured by amine titration method⁷ using dicinnamal acetone ($\text{pK}_a = -3.0$) as indicator.

Kinetic studies: 100 ml of 0.2M ester solution in double distilled water was taken in a 250 ml flask and 1 g of the catalyst was added. The contents of the flask were stirred uniformly by a magnetic stirrer. The reaction was allowed to proceed and the amount of hydrolysis taking place was estimated by titrating the liberated acid against standard alkali solution (protected from CO_2) at regular intervals of time. Reactions were carried out at 25° and 35° in a thermostat with temperature control arrangement with an accuracy of $\pm 0.01^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

It has been reported by Bernard *et al.*¹ that the hydrolysis of aliphatic ester catalysed by ion exchange resins is a first order reaction with respect

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of esters in presence of silica-alumina catalyst at 25°
○ Methylacetate
● Ethylacetate

to ester concentrations. This is similar to HCl catalysed homogeneous reactions². In the present investigation, the hydrolysis of methyl and ethylacetates in the presence of mixed oxide catalysts have been found to be reactions of first order with respect to ester concentration. It is shown in Fig. 1 that the plots of $2.303 \log a/(a-x)$ against time t for $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst lie on a good straight line. Similar straight lines were obtained for other mixed oxide catalysts. The values of the first order rate constant K determined from the slopes of these lines are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. The dependence of rate constant on the concentration of catalyst.

□ Methylacetate
○ Ethylacetate
— $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ Catalyst

In Fig. 2, the effect of varying the amount of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst on the rate of hydrolysis of esters has been shown. These results indicate that the specific rate of reaction catalysed by the solid acid is proportional to the concentration of the catalyst.

A reference to the values of K in Tables 1 and 2 indicates that the hydrolysis of methylacetate is faster than that of ethylacetate in the presence of these catalysts. The values of K decrease as the acidity of the catalyst decreases indicating that, the degree of hydrolysis depends on the acidity of the catalyst. The energy of activation E for the hydrolysis of methyl acetate is of the order of 5.9 K.cal/mole and, as expected from the relative values of rate constants, is higher than that for the hydrolysis of ethylacetate which is of the order of 8.3 K.cal/mole.

The rate constant values calculated from the hydrolysis of these esters in the presence of HCl (0.46 mmoles) are also included in these tables for comparison. The acidities of the catalysts, as calculated from the ratios of the rate constants and the molar strength of HCl, are given in Tables 1 and 2 along with the observed acidities which were measured by the *n*-butylamine titration method using dicinnamal acetone ($\text{pK}_a = -3.0$) as the indicator⁷. The calculated and observed values of the acidities are in good agreement with each other which shows that the acid centres of $\text{pK}_a \leq -3.0$ are able to catalyse the hydrolysis of these esters. To confirm this view, the catalysts were poisoned with dicinna-

TABLE 1. HYDROLYSIS OF METHYLACETATE

Sl. No.	Catalyst	$K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$		E K.cals/mole	K-HCl/K-Catalyst ratio (average)	Acidity mmoles/g.	
		25°	35°			Calc.	Obs.
1.	Silica-alumina	11.54	16.20	6.078	1.22	0.377	0.377
2.	Silica-zirconia	9.40	13.05	5.877	1.49	0.309	0.300
3.	Silica-titania	6.27	8.80	6.074	2.22	0.207	0.200
4.	Alumina-zirconia	5.10	7.10	5.930	2.75	0.169	0.167
5.	Titania-zirconia	4.60	6.44	6.030	3.04	0.151	0.150
6.	Alumina-titania	2.53	3.52	5.917	5.54	0.084	0.098
7.	HCl	14.00	19.50	5.937	—	—	0.460

TABLE 2. HYDROLYSIS OF ETHYLACETATE

Sl. No.	Catalyst	$K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$		E K.cals/mole	K-HCl/K-catalyst ratio (average)	Acidity mmoles/g.	
		25°	35°			Calc.	Obs.
1.	Silica-alumina	7.70	12.20	8.150	1.16	0.397	0.377
2.	Silica-zirconia	5.60	9.00	8.501	1.59	0.290	0.300
3.	Silica-titania	4.00	6.30	8.137	2.24	0.205	0.200
4.	Alumina-zirconia	3.30	5.30	8.493	2.69	0.171	0.167
5.	Titania-zirconia	2.80	4.40	8.101	3.20	0.144	0.150
6.	Alumina-titania	1.40	2.20	8.101	6.41	0.072	0.098
7.	HCl	8.80	14.20	8.373	—	—	0.460

malacetone and then used as catalysts in the hydrolysis of these esters. No hydrolysis took place in the presence of these poisoned catalysts. This lends support to the view that acid centres of $pK_a \leq -3.0$ are catalytically active for ester hydrolysis.

Fig. 3 gives the plots of the rate constants against the acidity measured at $pK_a \leq -3.0$, for all the catalysts and HCl (0.46 moles) for both methyl and ethyl acetates. These plots give a straight line indicating that the rate of hydrolysis is directly proportional to acidity of the catalyst and the points for HCl lie on this straight line. This shows that these catalysts behave very much like HCl or any other mineral acid in the hydrolysis of esters. Our observations that acid centres of $pK_a \leq -3.0$ are necessary for ester hydrolysis implies selectivity

Fig. 3. The dependence of catalytic activity for ester hydrolysis on the number of acidic centres.

in the use of acid centres of particular acid strength for particular reaction and this agrees with an earlier observation that acid centres of $pK_a \leq -3.0$ are necessary in the depolymerisation of paraldehyde,⁸ where also it has been shown that there is selectivity in the utilisation of acid centres. Since hydrolysis of esters takes place in the presence of these catalysts in aqueous media, it is confirmed that these catalysts exhibit acidic property even in the presence of water and this agrees with the observation made earlier by Figoli *et al.*³ and Matsuzaki⁴.

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